

MONITORING PODZEMNIH VODA SRBIJE – USLOV ZA NJIHOVO OPTIMALNO KORIŠĆENJE I ZAŠTITU OD ZAGAĐIVANJA

Zoran Stevanović, Saša Milanović,
Ljiljana Vasić, Branislav Petrović, Veljko Marinović
Rudarsko-geološki fakultet, Departman za hidrogeologiju, Beograd, Dušina 7
e-mail: zstev_2000@yahoo.co.uk

Rezime

Okvirna direktiva o vodama EU iz 2000. god. propisuje da je režim podzemnih voda osnovni parametar za definisanje njihovog kvantitativnog i kvalitativnog statusa. Parametri procene kvantitativnog statusa su ili nivo podzemnih voda ili procenjeni bilans tela podzemnih voda. Dobar kvantitativni status podrazumeva da je nivo podzemnih voda takav da dugoročno zahvatanje voda srednjim godišnjim kapacitetom ne prevazilazi raspoložive rezerve podzemnih voda. U Srbiji se još uvek ne raspolaže pouzdanim podacima o režimu nivoa i bilansu podzemnih voda u svim izdvojenim vodnim telima podzemnih voda. Ovo je uslovljeno nedostatkom kvalitetnih podataka, i neintegrativnom pristupu postojećim podacima.

Projektom koji su stručnjaci Rudarsko-geološkog fakulteta realizovali za potrebe Hidrometeorološkog zavoda Srbije (RHMZ) predložena je nova organizacija monitoring mreže, sa ukupno 33 grupe vodnih tela podzemnih voda. Projekcijom mreže obuhvaćen je ukupno 361 objekat, od čega bi 148 objekata bilo pod neposrednom ingerencijom RHMZ-a dok bi se njima priključilo i 213 objekata u okviru postojećih izvorišta podzemnih voda.

Pritisak na status kvaliteta podzemnih voda u ovom, i kasnije realizovanom projektu Operativnog monitoringa, ocenjivan je na osnovu Karte rizika od zagađivanja podzemnih voda difuznim zagađivačima, koja je dobijena kompilacijom postojeće Karte ugroženosti podzemnih voda i Karte hazarda od zagađivanja. Projekcijom mreže za kvalitativni monitoring obuhvaćeno je ukupno 130 objekata, od čega je 21 objekat iz postojeće mreže stanica Agencije za životnu sredinu Srbije. Predloženo je, slično kao i za kvantitativni monitoring, uvođenje u mrežu još 90 punktova, pretežno sa postojećih izvorišta ili nekaptiranih karstnih vrela.

U cilju prevazilaženja problema nedovoljnog monitoringa podzemnih voda, koji je uslov za optimalno korišćenje postojećih i razvoj novih izvorišta, potrebno je efektivnije i brže integrisanje neposrednih korisnika u sistem nacionalnog monitoringa, odnosno, ispunjavanje već zakonski propisanih obaveza monitoringa nivoa, izdašnosti i kvaliteta, ne samo tretirane i isporučene vode, već i „sirove“ (prirodne na vodozahvatima) i „prelivne“ vode (nazahvaćene količine).

Ključne reči: podzemne vode, vodno telo, monitoring, status voda

MONITORING OF GROUNDWATER IN SERBIA - A PREREQUISITE FOR ITS OPTIMAL USE AND PROTECTION FROM POLLUTION

Zoran Stevanović, Saša Milanović, Ljiljana Vasić,
Branislav Petrović, Veljko Marinović

*University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining & Geology, Department of Hydrogeology,
Belgrade, Djušina 7*

e-mail: zstev_2000@yahoo.co.uk

Abstract

Water Framework Directive of EU (2000) stipulates that the groundwater regime is the basic parameter for defining its quantitative and qualitative status. The quantitative status assessment parameters are either the groundwater level or the estimated water budget of the groundwater body. A good quantitative status implies that the level of groundwater is such that the long-term abstraction of water with the average annual capacity does not exceed the available groundwater reserves. In Serbia, there is still no reliable data on the regime of the level and groundwater budget in all separated water bodies. This is conditioned by the lack of quality data, and a non-integrative approach to existing data.

The project implemented by the experts of the Faculty of Mining and Geology for the needs of the Hydrometeorological Institute of Serbia (HIS) proposed a new organization of the monitoring network, with a total of 33 groups of groundwater bodies. The projection of the network includes a total of 361 water objects, of which 148 facilities would be under the direct authority of the HIS, while 213 facilities within the existing groundwater sources would be connected to them.

The pressure on the groundwater quality status in this, and the later implemented *Operational Monitoring* project, was assessed based on the Map of the risk of groundwater pollution by diffuse pollutants, which was obtained by compiling the existing groundwater Vulnerability map and Hazard map. The projection of the network for qualitative monitoring includes a total of 130 objects, of which 21 objects are from the existing network of stations of the Serbian Environmental Agency. It was proposed, similar to the quantitative monitoring, to introduce another 90 points into the network, mostly from existing springs or uncaptured karst springs.

In order to overcome the problem of insufficient monitoring of groundwater, which is a condition for the optimal use of existing and development of new sources, it is necessary to more effectively and quickly integrate direct water end-users into the national monitoring system, that is, to fulfill the already legally prescribed obligations of monitoring the level, yield and quality of not only treated and delivered water, but also “raw” (natural at water intakes) and “overflow” water (non-tapped quantities).

Key words: groundwater, water body, monitoring, water status